

*Climate and cultural based design and market valuable
technology solutions for Plus Energy Houses*

Position paper on policy development to foster the construction of PEBs

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Authors

Larissa De Rosso, Architects' Council of Europe

Lukas Bollaert, Architects' Council of Europe

Annamaria Belleri, Eurac Research

Roberto Lollini, Eurac Research

Cristian Pozza, Eurac Research

Herrmann Leis, SIZ Energieplus

Isabelle Büttner, SIZ Energieplus

John Einar Thommesen, SINTEF

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Executive summary

This document provides key recommendations for the policy development to foster the construction of PEB. The recommendations are drawn from the findings and results of the Cultural-E project, particularly the experiences gained from the four demonstrator cases. They are strongly supported by an analysis of relevant policy at the national level in France, Germany, Italy, Norway and at the European level.

The Cultural-E Project aims to advance the development of PEBs by integrating climate-responsive, culturally adapted smart technologies across Europe. The project approach is validated in four Plus Energy Buildings within four climatic and cultural zones encompassing France, Germany, Italy and Norway.

The Cultural-E project partners strongly believe that Plus Energy Buildings is a step further into Nearly Zero-Energy Building (NZEB) or zero-emission buildings (ZEB). The introduction of PEB into national law has the potential to be a game-changer in reducing greenhouse emissions and global warming.

This position paper aims to support policymakers in the implementation of PEB concepts and provide information for developers, building owners, architects, engineers, and design and construction professionals to foster the implementation of PEB in Europe.

1 Introduction

The European Green Deal ambition is to achieve climate neutrality in Europe by 2050 through the commitment of the 27 Member States to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. The European Climate Law converted this ambition into law in July 2021.

To align relevant European Directives with the Green Deal objectives, the Fit for 55 package included updates/revisions in three main Directives related to the building environment: the Energy Performance in Buildings Directive (EPBD), the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) and the Renewable Energy Efficiency Directive (RED). The update/revision of these directives approved by the European Council should be adapted into the national regulations by 2025. These three Directives complement each other in the call for ensuring a sustainable European building stock. They set minimum baselines aimed at achieving Zero-Emission Buildings (ZEB).

The recent updates on the Energy Performance in Buildings Directive (EPBD), the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), and the Renewable Energy Efficiency Directive (RED) provide an opportunity to implement new and more ambitious targets at the national level. To meet the Green Deal's goals and the targets outlined in these Directives, Member States will need to exceed the minimum requirements and actively promote the development of Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs).

This position paper aims to inform policymakers, developers, building owners, architects, engineers, and design and construction professionals about Cultural-E's main findings and results to foster the implementation of PEBs in Europe.

The Cultural-E Project aims to advance the development of PEBs by integrating climate-responsive, culturally adapted smart technologies across Europe. The project approach is being tested in four Plus Energy Buildings within four climatic and cultural zones: France, Germany, Italy, and Norway.

This position paper analyses the main elements of the relevant European Directives that support the advance of Plus Energy Buildings. At the national level, this position paper analyses relevant legal and policy barriers to the development of Plus Energy buildings and also provides best practices in France, Germany, Italy and Norway. The result is key recommendations to support and foster the development of Plus Energy Buildings in the implementation of European Directives at the National level.

2 Legislative background at the European level

2.1 Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)

Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings (recast)

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) aims to enhance the energy efficiency of buildings across the EU. It sets minimum energy performance requirements for new constructions, renovations, and existing buildings, promoting renewable energy use and requiring Member States to establish national renovation plans. The May 2024 revision accelerates building renovations, fosters smart technologies, and outlines a roadmap for a fully decarbonized building stock by 2050. While the directive sets minimum standards, it encourages Member States to exceed these requirements.

A core goal of the EPBD is for all new and renovated buildings to achieve at least Nearly Zero-Energy Building (NZEB) status, with an emphasis on transitioning toward Zero-Emission Buildings (ZEB). Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs), which generate more energy than they consume, align with these goals. Although the EPBD does not explicitly define PEBs, it references buildings with similar characteristics in Article 19, which introduces an optional Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) category, A+. This class applies to buildings with energy demands at least 20% below ZEB thresholds and with annual onsite renewable energy generation exceeding total primary energy demand.

While not mandating PEBs, the EPBD promotes the principles central to their design, including energy efficiency, renewable energy integration, and innovative building solutions.

Key provisions include:

- Energy efficiency and NZEB baseline: New buildings must achieve high energy performance and meet most energy demands with renewables. Deep renovation is prioritized to enhance energy efficiency in existing stocks.
- Monitoring and reporting: Energy performance measurement and certification ensure transparency and align with PEBs' emphasis on detailed energy balances.
- Smart readiness: The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) supports smart technologies, enabling flexible buildings that dynamically balance energy load and generation align with the integration of PEB technologies.

- Renewable energy systems: Integration of onsite and local renewable systems aligns with PEB's reliance on renewables within the building footprint or nearby.
- Indoor environmental quality: Standards for air quality and thermal comfort align with PEB principles of creating healthy, comfortable spaces.

The EPBD supports the broader transition to low-carbon, electrified buildings, emphasizing electrification as a key decarbonization pathway. While it doesn't mandate PEB adoption, it lays a strong foundation for its development through NZEB standards, renewable energy promotion, and smart technologies. Achieving widespread adoption of PEBs will require additional national policies, technical guidance, and financial mechanisms.

2.2 Energy Efficiency Directive (EED)

Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (recast)

The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) aims to enhance energy efficiency across the EU by setting binding targets for Member States to reduce energy consumption. Complementing the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), the EED outlines a series of measures to achieve these targets.

Although the EED does not explicitly mention Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs), their development aligns with the Directive's emphasis on energy efficiency, renewable energy integration, and building renovation. By prioritizing the integration of renewable energy technologies and smart systems into buildings—key components for PEB functionality—the EED indirectly supports their adoption. Its focus on energy efficiency and renovation strategies creates opportunities for constructing PEBs and retrofitting existing underperforming buildings to meet PEB standards.

2.3 Renewable Energy Directive (RED)

Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652

The Renewable Energy Directive (RED) sets binding targets to increase the share of renewable energy in the EU's gross final energy consumption. By streamlining administrative procedures, introducing support schemes, and requiring guarantees of origin for renewable energy, the RED aims to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy projects.

Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) align closely with the objectives of the RED, as they support increased renewable energy use and energy efficiency. The RED particularly advances PEB goals through:

- Simplified permitting – reducing administrative barriers for renewable installations and facilitating onsite systems in buildings.
- Renewable integration – encourages local and decentralized renewable energy solutions, which are central to PEBs.
- Innovation – promotes investment in renewable energy technologies critical for creating energy-surplus buildings.

By fostering renewable energy deployment and streamlining project implementation, the RED creates an enabling environment for advancing PEBs and supporting the EU's decarbonization objectives.

2.4 EPBD, EED and RED for Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs)

The EPBD, EED, and RED collectively drive the EU's vision of a low-carbon future and a sustainable building stock. While they do not mandate Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs), their frameworks support projects focused on energy efficiency, renewable energy integration, and technological innovation – key components for advancing PEB adoption. For a realistic path to achieving a zero-carbon future by 2050, Member States must exceed the minimum legal requirements outlined in these directives. Cultural-E partners call Member States to actively pursue PEB standards for both new and renovated buildings to ensure alignment with long-term decarbonization goals.

3 Policy context at National level in Norway, Italy, Germany and France

The Cultural-E project developed methodologies, technology sets and tools for the design, construction and monitoring of Plus Energy Buildings implementation in four climatic and cultural zones encompassing France, Germany, Italy and Norway. Although the result of this work provided evidence that Plus Energy Buildings can be achieved on the ground it also brought to light some legal barriers and good practices for Plus Energy Building implementation at the national level that are described below.

3.1 Overview of existing national policies in Norway in the context of PEB

Energy efficiency and the use of renewables in buildings have long been priorities in Norway, and these were particularly emphasised by the new Regulations on technical requirements for construction works in 2007 (TEK 07) and 2010 (TEK10). The insulation level required by the current TEK 17 fits well with PEB's ambitions for new buildings. Requirements for greenhouse gas accounting for building materials were implemented in 2022, and the use of PV and flexibility is a natural focus in ambitious projects. However, there are still policy-related barriers.

The Norwegian regulations do not require a building to be PEB, but the regulations are strict. These regulations ensure that the buildings are energy-efficient and environmentally friendly. The buildings must be designed and equipped with technology that minimizes energy consumption, including high-efficiency insulation, energy-efficient windows and doors, and advanced ventilation and heating systems. In addition, all new buildings must have an energy label, which provides information about the building's energy use and efficiency. This promotes transparency and encourages energy-efficient solutions.

The Norwegian demonstration is BREEAM-NOR Excellent certified. This means that the building demonstrates high performance in nine specific areas: management, health and indoor environment, energy, transport, water, materials, waste, land use and ecology, and pollution. If you certify after BREEAM-NOR, the regulations in (TEK17) will be fulfilled (and surpassed), and some buildings in Norway with Excellent ratings are PEB.

Many buildings in Norway are built as FutureBuilt projects. It is a program that started in 2010 with the aim of developing pilot projects (including individual buildings and city areas) designed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from transport, energy, and material consumption by at least 50%. The buildings involved in these projects are of high architectural quality and are planned and built with criteria well beyond today's building codes and practices in Norway. Many are passive houses and near Zero Energy

Buildings (nZEB). In Norway, there is an energetic level towards constructing these types of buildings.

Buildings with this level of rating don't, however, always have high Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) ratings. Which means that the building has the potential to be better. This is part of what we are investigating in the Norwegian demonstration. The SRI evaluates how well a building can optimise energy efficiency, adapt to occupants' needs, and respond to energy grid signals. In other words, SRI can describe a building's flexibility potential.

3.1.1 Legal and policy-related barriers to PEBs in Norway

Norway's energy policies heavily favour hydropower, which already supplies most of the country's electricity. Not only is this a renewable energy source, but it also has several desirable characteristics from a grid (storage potentials, fast and flexible ramping, balancing capabilities, black start services, frequency stabilization).

More than 75 % of the Norwegian production capacity is flexible. This means that production can rapidly be regulated up and down as needed. Combined with the accumulated storage capacity of about 100 TWh, hydropower (the whole system, from water storage to generators) can provide flexibility on a timescale from seconds (frequency regulation) to hours (congestion management, load matching) and months (seasonal flexibility). Historically, this has meant that the need for flexibility in the Norwegian power system has been low since hydropower has provided the desirable characteristics. This flexibility is, however, at the grid level. At the building level, other flexibility systems are important, and regulations are the tools to have these implemented.

The use of Heat Pumps (HP) and Photovoltaic (PV) panels are mainstream solutions for PEBs in Norway. Solar and water complement each other well in the Norwegian power system. Solar energy can contribute to increased utilisation of the capacity in our water reservoirs. Solar energy and energy efficiency measures in buildings can free electricity for other purposes. Solar energy in buildings provides new energy production without environmental impact. Local energy production further leads to reduced energy losses in the power grid.

Surplus energy solutions have been available in Norway since 2017, but regulatory barriers have prevented the sharing of produced energy, for instance, among tenants in apartment buildings.

From October 1, 2023, customers on the same farm and property number can utilize roof and wall surfaces to produce and consume their own electricity. This facilitates housing cooperatives, multi-family homes, commercial buildings, etc., to use self-

produced energy to cover their own consumption. A producer can share surplus production from production facilities up to 1 MW (1000 kW) with other customers on the same farm and property number.

However, housing cooperatives with multiple construction stages and separate garages often use different property numbers, which prevents them from sharing energy. To address this challenge, it is recommended to enable the coordination of flexible energy resources at the area level, including within apartment buildings. This could be achieved by organising such areas as energy communities.

For some areas, energy grid reinforcement is needed to implement the surplus energy, especially for larger PV areas. [WattApp](#) can give an overview of relevant areas. Increased self-consumption is evaluated, and Electric Vehicle (EV)-charging in the daytime, like in the Norwegian demonstration, is favourable. Load shed is demonstrated by the use of a local battery for peak hours, while load shift for domestic hot water heating offers significant flexibility. Increased access to flexible markets through lowering the size of bids, as well as communication platforms and tariffs for increased understanding and reward, is necessary.

Advanced technical systems for energy-efficient operation, use of PV production and flexibility potential require dedicated meters, sensors and other components, as well as advanced Building Management Systems (BMS). The role of a coordinator for Integrated Technical Building Installations (ITB) is acknowledged in NS 3935 and is highly necessary. This is an onsite representative from the project owner involved throughout the project. An ITB coordinator is a professional who assists building owners and general contractors with cross-disciplinary coordination of technical installations in buildings. After the building has been taken over by the user, there is also technical staff which handles and follows up the day-to-day control if necessary.

PV production, EV charging, and batteries are often managed through separate systems. To optimize their integration, unified systems that bridge these technologies are essential. However, implementing advanced systems with predictive control remains a challenge, as it is still in the early stages of practical application.

Also, targeted requirements and tests for the handover of technical facilities and procedures for fault detection in trial operations are recommended before implementing flexibility.

3.1.2 Best Policy Practices for PEB in Norway

Norway follows many of the EU's rules and directives through the EEA Agreement, even though Norway is not a member of the EU. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) requires that all new buildings must be nearly zero-energy buildings (nZEB) by 2021. However, Norway has not yet accepted this directive. Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) is, however, being followed. This directive requires member states to implement measures to improve energy efficiency in buildings, including the renovation of existing buildings and the introduction of energy management systems.

TEK 17 set the rules for energy-efficient buildings in Norway, and these regulations are strict. The minimum requirement for insulation is, for example, the following:

- U-value outer walls: $\leq 0.22 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$
- U-value roof: $\leq 0.18 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$
- U-value floors on the ground and open air: $\leq 0.18 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$
- U-value windows and doors, including frames: $\leq 1.2 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$

With these requirements and additional technical equipment and installation, PEB houses are possible. For instance, the use of heat pumps is very common, even in private homes, and there are support schemes from the government to help with the costs.

Passive house standard is not a mandatory requirement for new buildings but can be seen as a reference for PEB. Many new buildings follow this standard since TEK17 lays the foundation with its strict regulations. Criteria for residential buildings are given in the Norwegian standard NS 3700:2013.

Using the roofs for the installation of additional equipment to reach PEBs is common, but there is "competition" for that area. PV is, on the one hand, important for reaching the PEB goals, but also water retention and recreational areas are important. We, therefore, have a guide on how to construct these blue-green roofs. A blue-green roof offers a range of benefits by combining vegetation (green roof) with water management (blue roof). Some of the benefits are temporary storage of water, promotion of biodiversity, improved thermal insulation, and improved air quality. Blue/green roofs can also contribute to achieving credits under various BREEAM categories.

3.2 Overview of existing national policies in Italy in the context of PEB

In Italy, various legal and policy barriers hinder the widespread adoption of Positive Energy Buildings (PEBs), as highlighted by the Italian demonstration project. These challenges stem from complex bureaucratic processes, fragmented regulations between national and regional levels, and a focus on retrofitting existing buildings rather than building new ones. Although incentives for renewable energy integration and energy communities are evolving, the current legislative landscape does not fully support the creation of self-sufficient, energy-positive buildings.

3.2.1 Legal and policy-related barriers to PEBs in Italy

The implementation of Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) in Italy faces several significant barriers, as evidenced by our experience with the Cultural-E demonstration project in Castenaso, Bologna. These barriers stem from both regulatory frameworks and market conditions shaped by national policies.

A primary challenge encountered during the project was the profound market distortion created by the Superbonus 110% policy (tax deduction of 110% for expenses incurred up to 31 December 2023, 70% for expenses incurred in 2024, and 65% for expenses incurred in 2025). The deduction is only applicable if, by 15 October 2024, the certified notification of the beginning of works has been submitted. While designed to promote energy efficiency renovations, this policy inadvertently created significant obstacles for new PEB construction. During the demonstration project's implementation phase, construction costs escalated to critical levels due to market-wide material price inflation (also due to other factors happening at the same time, i.e. disruption of the supply chain in China for plastics and electronics, flooding heavily affecting the area, etc...). Additionally, the policy created an acute shortage of skilled workers and specialised personnel, as contractors were overwhelmed with renovation projects (and locally also involved in reconstruction after flooding). This shortage led to substantial delays even in standard construction activities such as insulation installation and contracting of specialised companies, directly impacting the project timeline and costs.

Another significant barrier emerged from regulatory limitations on energy sharing within multi-unit buildings. The regulatory framework (which changed since the design phase) forced sub-optimal system designs by restricting internal energy-sharing capabilities. In the Castenaso demonstration project, this limitation resulted in the installation of separate electrical, photovoltaic, and battery storage systems for each dwelling, along with individual allocation of rooftop PV surface area. This fragmentation prevented the implementation of more efficient collective systems and energy sharing that could have optimised energy production and consumption across all units, as well as better

interaction with the power grid. The regulation of buildings with shared energy systems as large-scale producers rather than prosumers further complicated the implementation of integrated energy solutions.

The Italian regulatory landscape presents additional challenges through its complex bureaucratic processes. The fragmented system requires compliance with both national and regional regulations, often leading to inconsistencies and project delays. Current legislation evaluates only specific energy consumption aspects, such as heating, cooling, ventilation and domestic hot water production, while excluding other energy uses like lighting and household appliances. The latest has a significant impact on the overall energy consumption of low-energy residential buildings. This limited scope restricts the comprehensive assessment of building energy performance and hinders the evaluation of PEBs at the community level. Building energy performance calculation methods are based on standard usage assumptions, overlooking the specific needs and habits of residents. As a result, there is often a discrepancy between the expected performance outlined in energy certifications and the actual performance of the building. Additionally, the legislation mandates the use of building automation and control systems solely for non-residential buildings, thus limiting the potential for users to actively reduce energy consumption in residential settings.

The focus of Italian legislation has shifted from prioritizing energy efficiency improvements to promoting the increased use of renewable energy. Recent legislative updates introduce various incentive schemes to support the installation of photovoltaic systems on buildings and the sharing of the energy they produce.

Legislative Decree 28/2011 mandates integrating renewable energy systems (e.g., PV systems) and has been recently updated by increasing the required share of Domestic Hot Water (DHW) and heating and cooling covered by renewable energy (up to 80% for buildings built or retrofitted after January 2026) and the required PV power installed in new constructions and renovation. Despite it being a step forward for self-sufficient buildings, the requirements are not ambitious enough to foster PEBs and do not require the use of thermal and electricity storage systems.

As regards the definition and implementation of the Renewable Energy Community (REC) in Italy (Legislative Decree 199/2021), there is a distinction between “collective self-consumption” and REC. The first one is dedicated to the single-building multi-family house (at least two users), while the second one considers the energy shared among more than one building, as reported. In Italy, REC can be created by observing two parameters: geographical proximity and the same primary substation affiliation. The legislation uses a ‘virtual’ network model, where the energy community is made of virtual nodes not belonging to the same secondary cabin but extending the domain to the

primary substation. The shared and the self-consumed energy are incentivised. For collective self-consumption, an agreement between the condominium members (or the inhabitants of the same building) is sufficient, while for REC, a formal agreement at a legal level is required. Given the different modalities, collective self-consumption and REC present different difficulties in becoming a reality. In one case, a unanimous agreement is required, which is often difficult to obtain, while in the second case, it is necessary to deal with the bureaucracy and be competent in REC matters. Household commitment and economic sustainability are key elements to foster the implementation of REC and collective self-consumption. At present, the higher the energy the building can share, the higher the economic viability is. In order for energy communities to fully express their potential and for PEBs to be part of it, it will be essential to continue to promote incentive policies.

The main barriers to participation in the Italian demonstration case for collective self-consumption stem from the complex authorisation and association procedures, which were perceived as lengthy and complicated.

The incentive schemes for photovoltaic systems in Italy are changing rapidly. The general aim of the latest incentives and benefits is to reward self-consumption and combat energy poverty.

The National Energy Income Fund offers non-repayable grants for the installation of photovoltaic systems for low-income families (Decreto 8/08/2023 – Fondo Nazionale Reddito Energetico). It aims at increasing the amount of PV plants in self-consumption assets in the southern regions.

For new constructions, tax deduction can cover up to 65% of the incurred expenses for the installation of grid-connected photovoltaic solar systems on condominiums, as well as for the installation of storage systems integrated into the aforementioned incentivised photovoltaic solar systems. The Superbonus applies only if the photovoltaic system is installed alongside major energy efficiency or seismic safety interventions, as specified by Decree Law 34/2020, and subsequent updates.

The financial contributions due to collective self-consumption schemes include a compensation value granted on the self-consumed electricity and a premium tariff granted on the shared energy ([D.M. 414/2023](#)).

Non-repayable grants (bonus “*colonnine domestiche*”) covering up to 80% of the costs for the acquisition and installation of Electrical Vehicle charging stations are available for private citizens and multi-family houses (for installations in common areas).

As of January 2025, Italy is in the process of adopting the European Union's Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) 2024/1275, which mandates that all new residential and non-residential buildings be zero-emission by January 1, 2030.

The Autonomous Province of Bolzano has proactively aligned with this directive by approving a regulation on October 22, 2024, requiring all new constructions to be "zero-energy" buildings starting from January 1, 2030. This initiative is part of Bolzano's Climate Plan 2040, aiming for carbon neutrality in the building sector by 2050. The regulation also offers incentives covering up to 80% of expenses for energy efficiency improvements, encouraging the transition to sustainable building practices.

At the national level, Italy is working towards integrating the EPBD's requirements into its legislative framework.

3.2.2 Best Policy Practices for PEB in Italy

Despite these challenges, several emerging policy practices demonstrate potential for supporting PEB development in Italy. The experience gained from projects like Cultural-E provides valuable insights for policy improvement.

Progressive regional initiatives are leading the way in PEB support. The Autonomous Province of Bolzano's proactive adoption of zero-energy building requirements by 2030, coupled with substantial incentives covering up to 80% of energy efficiency improvements, provides a model for other regions to follow. This approach demonstrates how local authorities can advance beyond national requirements to foster innovative building solutions.

Recent policy developments have introduced support mechanisms that could benefit PEB implementation. These include the national energy income fund for low-income families, tax deductions for integrated PV systems in condominiums, and financial incentives for collective self-consumption. The framework for energy communities, while still evolving, provides a foundation for expanding PEB impact beyond individual buildings.

Based on the Cultural-E project experience, several policy improvements would significantly facilitate PEB development. First, incentive schemes should be designed to maintain market equilibrium between retrofitting and new PEB construction, including mechanisms to prevent market distortions. Second, regulations should be updated to enable optimal energy sharing within buildings, allowing for integrated systems that maximise efficiency and reduce costs. Third, workforce development programs should be established to ensure the availability of skilled professionals for PEB construction and operation.

The legislative framework for renewable energy integration, while progressive, requires further enhancement to fully support PEB development. Current requirements, such as those in Legislative Decree 199/2021, should be strengthened to include provisions for energy storage systems and more ambitious renewable energy integration targets. Additionally, comprehensive energy performance assessment frameworks should be developed to evaluate PEB contributions at both building and district levels.

Success in promoting PEB development will require a coordinated approach that addresses both technical and market barriers while providing stable, long-term support for innovation in the building sector.

3.3 Overview of existing national policies in Germany in the context of PEB

The construction and implementation of Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) in Germany is possible. However, there are some policy-related barriers as well as supporting legal measurements that need to be considered. These are summarised in what follows.

3.3.1 Legal and policy-related barriers to PEBs in Germany

The German Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV), now integrated into the Building Energy Act (GEG), considers for the building evaluation only the energy consumption for heating, domestic hot water production, auxiliaries (e.g. heating pumps) and ventilation, excluding cooling, lighting and household appliances. This narrow focus limits comprehensive evaluations of energy efficiency, making it challenging to evaluate PEBs potential contribution at the community or district level.

The overlap of federal and state-level authorities in enforcing building and energy regulations complicates compliance. Simplifying and harmonizing these frameworks, as partially addressed in the GEG, remains a work in progress.

The market of produced PV power is highly regulated, which makes it difficult for the landlord to sell the power to tenants.

The Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) 2017 levy on electricity cost was among the policy barriers at first but it has been significantly amended over time, with the latest version being the EEG 2023. The abolition of the EEG levy on electricity costs as of July 2022 eased the financial burden on consumers promoting renewable energy integration into the market more efficiently.

3.3.2 Best Policy Practices for PEB in Germany

In Germany, VAT for PV and battery installations is omitted. In other words, Germany is promoting renewable energy integration and, with that the implementation of PEBs.

In Germany, the requirement for the insulation fits well those necessary for PEB. In addition, for new Buildings a certain capacity of PV modules on the roof is mandatory. This regulation is a good basis for the PEB.

For getting a fund from the KfW (the national funding institution), the requirements go beyond the plus-energy idea. Here, a GWP value of a maximum of 24 kg CO₂/m²*a, considering additionally the grey emission of the construction is required to get a fund. How to reach this is not defined but the PEB-idea is a possibility to reach the goal. Indirectly, these funding criteria support the construction of PEBs.

3.4 Overview of existing national policies in France in the context of PEB

The latest version of the French environmental regulation for buildings, RE2020 (Réglementation Environnementale 2020), was published in 2022 and introduced a major change focusing on the overall carbon balance. There are now two main criteria, one related to energy performance and one associated with Global Warming contribution, considering the full life cycle of the building. This regulation applies to new buildings, and by being more ambitious, the mandatory threshold for energy consumption was lowered and, therefore, eased the path towards PEB. But while there was a PEB (BBEPOS - Bâtiment à Energie Positive) in the previous version (RT2012) there is no definition of PEB in the RE2020. Nevertheless, a label, as an extent of the regulation, defined it. But the non-official character of it is a limitation.

Nevertheless, the “BEPOS” (PEB) Label by Effinergie opens the door to new subsidies from the French government. Social housing organisations that build PEBs are now entitled to new subsidies, 0% interest loans, and, depending on where the PEB is located, local subsidies. This boosts the construction of PEBs; however, these subsidies do not cover the extra cost of building a PEB compared to a building built according to minimum RE2020 regulations.

Nuclear power accounts for the largest part of French electricity production, so electricity-based heating, DHW, or cooling is favored in the carbon lifecycle evaluation. Economic incentives for installing PV panels and purchasing electricity have lowered over the years and almost no longer exist.

3.4.1 Legal and policy-related barriers to PEBs in France

Current regulations tend to prioritize reducing energy consumption over cutting CO₂ emissions, which, while important, is less effective in achieving overarching climate goals.

The application of VAT on photovoltaic (PV) systems increases the upfront investment costs of renewable energy technologies. Although financial mechanisms such as zero-

rate loans (e.g., PTZ) provide some relief, these measures only partially address the economic burden, leaving financial barriers in place for many stakeholders.

Another key obstacle lies in the structure of existing incentive programs, which primarily target building renovations rather than new PEB projects. This focus slows the adoption of advanced, energy-efficient building technologies in new construction, reducing opportunities to incorporate cutting-edge innovations that could drive the transition to energy-positive buildings. Overcoming these policy challenges is crucial to accelerating the widespread implementation of PEBs and aligning construction practices with ambitious climate objectives.

The main barrier to the construction of PEB lies in the energy code, and in particular, Article 331-1. This article enshrines the freedom for everyone to contract with the energy supplier of their choice. This means that every tenant in the social housing sector, whether living in a PEB or not, can choose their energy supplier and not consume locally produced energy. The landlord cannot force the tenant to consume the energy produced on-site. The benefit is, therefore, limited, as it is assumed that landlords will enter into an energy supply contract with each voluntary tenant and sell the surplus if necessary. In practice, this management is possible, but in reality, it does not encourage landlords to enter into this type of contract.

The regulations are changing, and a new regulatory framework allows for the creation of energy communities in which the landlord/energy producer can draw up a supply contract with homes and businesses within a radius of 2 km, or even 20 km, by way of derogation in very rural areas. The regulations are, therefore, moving in the right direction, with the possibility for landlords to resell electricity to compensate for the additional cost of installing energy production equipment, but it is too early to see this type of community already appearing, as setting them up is complex.

3.4.2 Best Policy Practices to PEB in France

A good practice that allows for the construction of positive energy buildings, whether for agricultural facilities, offices or housing, is the third-party investor mechanism. The Article L315-1 of the Energy Code provides the legislative framework for self-consumption with a third-party investor:

“The self-producer’s installation may be owned or managed by a third party. The third-party may be entrusted with the installation and management, including maintenance, of the production installation, provided that it remains subject to the instructions of the self-producer. The third party itself is not considered a self-producer.”

The consumer is considered to be a self-producer and will, therefore, be the holder of the purchase contract and the grid access contract. In all cases, if the electricity is not consumed entirely on-site, the surplus must be resold.

A third-party investor may be involved in an individual self-consumption operation. In this case, the third-party investor's remuneration may take several forms:

1. In this first case, a 'local contract' may be signed between the third-party investor and the consumer, in which the purchase price of the electricity is set by mutual agreement between the two parties. A metering device is generally installed to count the kWh produced and thus establish the billing.

2. In this second case, a standard 'rental' contract may be signed between the third-party investor and the consumer, specifying the amount of the rent. Rules for adjusting this rent may be added depending on the difference between the plant's actual availability rate and a negotiated guaranteed availability rate.

In both cases, if the consumer is not the owner of the building (a tenant, for example), a contract between the third-party investor and the owner of the building sets out the conditions for occupying the roof.

A special case is that in which a public body makes its roof available to a third-party investor and wishes to self-consume part of the photovoltaic production. In this case, it is recommended to use a set-up that allows the obligations arising from the public order to be met.

These regulations are now accepted and understood by many landowners, and companies have been set up whose sole business model is third-party investment in photovoltaic production. This makes the roof space profitable for the landowner, who rents out the roof surface, and for the third-party investor, who sells the energy produced either directly on-site or by feeding it back into the general grid.

4 Key Policy Recommendations on Plus Energy Buildings

The previous chapter of this document highlighted the barriers and best practices at the national level in Norway, Italy, Germany and France and provided an overview of the European Directive landscape on renewable energy and energy efficiency in buildings. This chapter aims to summarise the key policy recommendations on Plus Energy Buildings based on the knowledge shared in the previous chapters.

Cultural-E partners strongly support the adoption of these key policy recommendations into national and European policy frameworks to achieve a balance between occupant satisfaction, energy efficiency, and the goals of Positive Energy Buildings, ensuring both environmental and social sustainability.

The key policy recommendations are summarised below.

- to harmonise regulations by establishing unified European standards for PEBs that consider lifecycle energy use and environmental impact considering the adoption of the Plus Energy Building definition provided by the Cultural-E project.
- to implement the co-benefits estimations to provide clear value of the benefits to the users, to the community, to the environment and to the society of Plus Energy Buildings projects ([Guidelines to assess the co-benefits of Plus Energy Buildings](#)).
- to adopt of a fixed target value $\leq 2 \text{ kgCO}_2/(\text{m}^2\text{y})$ for Plus Energy Buildings during the building operation phase. This target includes the assessment of all energy demand in the building, considering building heating, domestic hot water, ventilation, auxiliaries, building cooling, lighting and user appliances.
- to use Plus Energy Buildings Key Performance Indicators as defined in the [Cultural-E factsheet](#).
- to develop a better legal framework for the trading of energy surpluses by private individuals to promote the implementation of PEBs.
- to develop future clean energy funding programmes to subsidise CO₂-saving energy concepts and propose.
- To include bioclimatic design principles in national legislation while promoting the use of digital twins and modelling to support architectural design. This aims to optimise solar gain control and visual comfort, considering various boundary conditions and related dynamics. Additionally, it focuses on building adaptability to accommodate potential uses and context changes while continuing to exploit daylight, natural ventilation, and thermal inertia.
- To give priority to the inclusion of local providers in the supply chain as well as locally used and reconditioned components and materials.

- to support the upskilling and education of professionals to fulfil the new professional role of Integration Manager in the design, build and operation of Plus Energy Buildings.
- to facilitate the inclusion of training and certification schemes for professional upskilling regarding new technologies available in the market.
- to support the inclusion of a mandatory information session and/or home guides for building users/owners, including practical advice for reducing energy consumption and improving indoor air quality.
- To support the creation of a repository at the EU level to disclose building performance monitoring data, particularly for demonstration buildings supported within collaborative research projects. This repository would be invaluable in informing design and establishing benchmarks for building performance.
- to support the standardisation of common metrics for monitoring data to ensure a systematic and structured collection and access to a unique entry point repository.
- to promote dynamic thermal environments that accommodate regional differences in thermal comfort and adaptive behaviours, as well as to promote the use of personalised comfort systems and smart air movement in Building codes.
- to promote ongoing occupant feedback collection through surveys or interviews as part of the building's lifecycle management.
- to expand incentives by extending financial support to both new construction and innovative energy technologies.
- to promote sector coupling by encouraging district-level approaches that integrate electricity, heating, and mobility systems, as these can amplify GHG emission reduction compared to individual buildings.

4.1 PEB definition framework

Cultural-E partners (Oddo, Bigano, Bosello, & Giannini, 2024) put forward the Plus Energy Building definition below.

A Plus Energy Building is an energy-efficient building that produces more final energy than it uses via locally available renewable sources over a time span of one year. Building uses include both building operation and user-related energy consumption. The positive balance shall be reached while ensuring the lowest greenhouse gas emissions and a good dynamic matching between load and generation, according to economic affordability and technical viability.

The definition applies to all-electric buildings and the energy balance is based on measured or predicted final energy between load and generation (1).

The energy generation shall be performed by renewable energy systems located within the building footprint and can be extended to adjacent lots as long as there is a physical connection and direct control of renewable energy generation system relying on ownership of the buildings or lots, neighbourhood grid infrastructure and building management. Besides the plus energy balance verification, PEBs shall ensure an added value to the context by providing building flexibility and easy access to e-mobility and to final users by providing accessible, comfortable, and healthy indoor environments.

In case of new buildings, electrification is an inevitable process. In case other renewable energy vectors are used in the building (i.e., biomass, biogas...), the final energy balance shall be zero. (p. 10)

4.2 Value co-benefits

Co-benefits are added values to the building users, owner, and community that go beyond the direct and measurable impacts of high-efficiency energy buildings. The co-benefits identified in four domains by Cultural-E project partners are the following (Oddo, Bigano, Bosello, & Giannini, 2024).

- Public Health – Reduction of public health costs due to the improvement of indoor environmental quality, and reduction of local pollution leading to an overall improvement of dwellers' health and well-being.
- Energy poverty – Lower energy consumption leads to lower energy bills. Lower energy demand and dependency on the energy grid leads to reduction of fossil fuel dependency and import costs.
- Energy transition – contribution to the building sector decarbonization and stimulation electromobility.
- Sustainability – reduction of CO₂ emissions and natural resources use. Increasing resilience to climate change mitigating the urban heat island effect.

The Cultural-E project team developed methodologies for co-benefit estimations ([D5.2 'Guidelines to assess the co-benefits of PEBs'](#)) to provide clear value estimation of the benefits to the users, to the community, to the environment and to the society.

Cultural-E, methodological approach (Co-benefits analysis), as well as technologies (e.g. ceiling fan analysis or compact HP for domestic use), provides a framework for the

development of Affordable Housing Initiatives as a key element of the New European Bauhaus (NEB).

4.3 Set CO₂ Targets

Cultural-E partners recommend a fixed target value of $\leq 2 \text{ kgCO}_2/(\text{m}^2\text{y})$ for Plus Energy Buildings during the building operation phase. This target includes the assessment of all energy demand in the building considering building heating, domestic hot water, ventilation, auxiliaries, building cooling, lighting and user appliances. The fixed target approach should replace the building reference method.

Cultural-E partners support the cost of 180 € per ton CO₂ with an increase of up to 240 € per ton CO₂ by 2050 put forward by the German Federal Environment Agency to cover the cost of climate change's negative impacts. (Idler, et al., 2020)

4.4 Comprehensive performance evaluation

Cultural-E partners released factsheets with standardised information for the evaluation and assessment of Plus Energy Buildings. This information results from several analysis processes, including building energy simulation, life cycle environmental impact assessment and economical assessment of life cycle costs. The Factsheet presents clear information about the building type, the solution set, the climatic region, energy load, load matching and grid interaction, Life Cycle Assessment, Indoor Comfort, Economic impact and the residents' voices (Isaia, Turrin, Leis, Di Bari, & Pineda, 2023), concerning two residential building archetypes in four climates. An example of a factsheet can be found in Annex 2.

4.5 Energy surplus trading as a business model

The Cultural-E partners consider the German landlord-tenant electricity contract a positive approach to business models for energy surplus trading. Under this agreement, no grid fees, levies or charges are incurred on the electricity generated, supplied and consumed within the customer's facility (Büttner & Leis, 2024). Still, the sale of surplus energy from private individuals to private individuals represents a high administrative burden, as they are defined as energy suppliers. The Cultural-E partners call for the development of a better legal framework for the trading of energy surpluses by private individuals to promote the implementation of PEBs (Büttner & Leis, 2024).

In the research, it was found that PEBs could aid Renewable Energy Communities (REC). However, the Cultural-E partners consider the implementation of the RED II into national law as an obstacle to RECs, as financial charges for energy fed into the grid and grid fees do not provide an incentive for the further implementation of renewable energy

communities. In particular, the legal basis that communities involved in renewable energy are not allowed to act for profit is an obstacle for investors and innovative BMs, such as REC portfolios (Büttner & Leis, 2024). This is hindering the widespread implementation of PEBs within RECs.

4.6 Foster Plus Energy Communities

Cultural-E partners recommend the introduction of a district-level rather than individual building assessment approach for Plus Energy projects. This approach provides better possibilities for storage and flexibility in energy demand and generation, contributes to e-mobility on site and can help the community energy balance when heritage buildings are included. Communities also foster participatory decision-making processes helping to regain trust in the democratic life. (Büttner & Leis, 2024)

4.7 Subsidise CO₂ savings

Cultural-E partners recommend that future clean energy funding programmes subsidise CO₂-saving energy concepts and propose the following mechanisms (Idler, et al., 2020).

- 1) pay taxes when targets according to the individual climate protection plans are not met; or
- 2) a subsidization of real CO₂ savings, if they are already being achieved beyond the targets.

The consortium also recommends funding schemes to include in the portfolio alternative construction methods, such as lightweight or hybrid construction (reduced CO₂ emissions compared to reinforced concrete or masonry) (Idler, et al., 2020).

4.8 Building professionals' training and qualification

Cultural-E partners identified the need for a new professional role in the design, build and operation of Plus Energy Buildings. The Integration Manager is responsible for the coordination of all technologies on site, ensuring their smooth interaction and operation within the building life cycle.

Cultural-E partners call for the inclusion of training and certification schemes for professional upskilling regarding new technologies available in the market. Education of students and professional upskilling is a key factor for the up taking of Plus Energy Buildings in Europe.

4.9 Empower users

Plus Energy Buildings need empowered and aware users. The launch of awareness campaigns would help users understand the relationship between their daily practices and the building's energy performance.

Cultural-E partners recommend the inclusion of a mandatory information session and/or home guides for building users/owners including practical advice for reducing energy consumption and improving indoor air quality.

Cultural-E partners recognized the need to foster a cultural shift towards acceptance of variable indoor climates by educating occupants on how adaptability can improve comfort without excessive energy use.

4.10 Support personalized and interactive technologies

Cultural-E partners call for the building systems companies to offer an intuitive and user-friendly interface integration system bringing the design of the PEB technologies closer to the resident's needs and providing occupants with actionable feedback on energy use and indoor environmental quality (IEQ). (Isaia, Turrin, Leis, Di Bari, & Pineda, 2023)

Cultural-E partners also promote the adoption of technologies and systems that enable personalised control over heating, cooling, and ventilation, which enhance user satisfaction while reducing overall energy consumption (if the user is properly guided).

Cultural-E partners welcome investments in Research and Development for cost-effective personal heating and cooling devices that allow occupants to manage their comfort and can interact with the whole building systems.

4.11 Tailor Policies to Cultural and Geographical Contexts

Cultural-E partners recognise that comfort expectations differ by climate and culture and recommend using contextualised data (e.g., acceptability rates and operative temperatures) to inform standards and design guidelines. Building codes shall promote dynamic thermal environments to accommodate regional differences in thermal comfort and adaptive behaviours.

4.12 Enhance Occupant Engagement and Feedback Mechanisms

Cultural-E partners recommend continuous occupant feedback collection through surveys or interviews as part of the building's lifecycle management. This ensures designs and systems evolve with user needs and preferences.

By integrating these strategies into policy frameworks, policymakers can help achieve a balance between occupant satisfaction, energy efficiency, and the goals of Positive Energy Buildings, ensuring both environmental and social sustainability.

4.13 Promote user-centred design

Cultural-E partners recommend the prioritisation of user needs, cultural contexts, and socio-climatic practices in the design and operation of Positive Energy Buildings (PEBs). Develop and mandate user-centric design frameworks that allow occupants to influence their indoor environments based on individual preferences and localised comfort expectations.

Cultural-E partners support the inclusion of bioclimatic design principles in national legislation while promoting the use of digital twins and modelling to support architectural design. This aims to optimise solar gain control and visual comfort, considering various boundary conditions and related dynamics. Additionally, it focuses on building adaptability to accommodate potential uses and context changes while continuing to exploit daylight, natural ventilation, and thermal inertia. It should also give priority for the inclusion of local providers in the supply chain.

Cultural-E promotes PEBs by sharing information about real cases in an online HUB. The PEB HUB aims to be a repository of information for reference and use in the field (Annex 3).

4.14 Monitoring data disclosure as a tool to inform the design process

Cultural-E partners strongly support the creation of a repository at the EU level to disclose building performance monitoring data to inform the design and create benchmarks on the actual performance of the buildings, particularly for demonstration buildings supported within collaborative research projects.

The partners also support the standardisation of common metrics for monitoring data to ensure a systematic and structured collection and access to a unique entry point repository.

It also supports the learning curve for people's well-being in energy-efficient homes and the high energy efficiency of the building system. Data is knowledge at the Service of People.

5 Conclusions

This position paper gathers the results and findings of five years of Cultural-E project research and provides recommendations for policy developments that will foster the implementation of the Plus Energy Building at the National and European levels.

Although Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) are not mandated in the European Directives EPBD, EED and RED, their frameworks support projects focused on energy efficiency (nZEB/ZEB), renewable energy integration, and technological innovation, which are key components for advancing PEB adoption at the national level. For a concrete achievement of the European Green Deal targets, the minimum legal requirements set in these directives must be exceeded. Therefore, Cultural-E partners call for Member States to introduce PEB standards into the national transposition of the European Directives for both new and renovated buildings to give concrete steps to achieve climate neutrality of the building stock by 2050.

The overview of the national regulations, barriers and best practices in Norway, Italy, Germany and France shows that most of the countries are progressing on regulations that increase the share of renewable energy technologies and energy efficiency in buildings, but Plus Energy Buildings are still a topic that is not covered at National Level, including advancements on energy communities and better models for the commercialisation of buildings energy surplus and energy storage initiatives.

In Norway, energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings have long been a priority in the country, supported by strict regulations like TEK 17 and programs such as FutureBuilt, which promote low-carbon, high-quality construction. National policies require high insulation standards, energy-efficient systems, and energy labelling for new buildings, aligning with Plus Energy Building (PEB) ambitions. Initiatives such as BREEAM-NOR certification and advancements in photovoltaic (PV) technology, heat pumps, and smart energy systems demonstrate progress. However, legal and policy barriers persist, including challenges with surplus energy sharing, fragmented regulations for housing cooperatives, and limited integration of advanced energy management systems. Hydropower's dominance provides grid-level flexibility but reduces emphasis on building-level energy solutions. Norway follows EU energy efficiency directives, though the adoption of the nearly zero-energy building (nZEB) directive remains incomplete. Efforts to optimize rooftop space with PV and blue-green roofs highlight a balance between energy production and environmental sustainability.

In Italy, the legal and policy barriers to adopting Positive Energy Buildings (PEBs) are significant, including bureaucratic complexity, fragmented regulations, and a focus on retrofitting over new construction. Initiatives like the Cultural-E demonstration reveal issues such as market distortions from the Superbonus 110% policy, which inflated

construction costs and caused labour shortages, and restrictive energy-sharing regulations within multi-unit buildings. Current legislation emphasises renewable energy integration but lacks provisions for energy storage and comprehensive performance assessment. Emerging practices, like the Autonomous Province of Bolzano's zero-energy building requirements and national incentives for PV systems and collective energy use, highlight progress. Policy improvements, including balanced incentives, enabling energy sharing, workforce development, and strengthened renewable energy mandates, are essential for advancing PEB development in Italy. A coordinated strategy addressing technical and market challenges will be critical to achieving long-term innovation and sustainability in the building sector.

In Germany, the overall policy landscape supports the implementation of Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) but includes certain barriers. Regulations like the Building Energy Act (GEG) limit energy evaluations by excluding cooling, lighting, and household appliances while overlapping federal and state authorities' complicate compliance. Although previously restrictive, amendments such as the abolition of the EEG levy have eased financial barriers, and VAT exemptions for PV and battery installations encourage renewable energy adoption. Mandatory PV installation and insulation standards align with PEB requirements, and funding criteria from KfW incentivise sustainable construction, indirectly supporting PEB development by encouraging low-carbon and energy-efficient solutions.

In France, the RE2020 environmental regulation, introduced in 2022, emphasises carbon balance and lifecycle environmental impact alongside energy performance, encouraging the transition toward Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs). Despite progress, challenges persist, such as a lack of an official PEB definition in RE2020 and insufficient subsidies to offset higher construction costs. Regulatory barriers include prioritising energy consumption reduction over CO₂ emissions, VAT on photovoltaic systems, and tenant freedom to choose energy suppliers, which complicates on-site energy utilization. However, positive strides include the "BEPOS" label for PEB that enables access to subsidies, the development of energy communities, and the third-party investor model allowing external investment in self-consumption systems. These mechanisms support energy-positive construction while enabling landowners and third-party investors to share economic benefits, fostering innovation and sustainable building practices.

In summary, Cultural-E partners recommend harmonising European standards for Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) to account for lifecycle energy use and environmental impact, adopting clear definitions and fixed targets such as a ≤ 2 kgCO₂/(m²y) threshold during building operation. It is also important to emphasize the importance of demonstrating co-benefits for users, communities, and the environment while proposing improved

legal frameworks for energy surplus trading and enhanced funding for CO₂-saving energy solutions. The recommendations highlight integrating bioclimatic design principles, promoting adaptability, and prioritizing local supply chains. They also call for upskilling professionals, introducing the role of Integration Manager, mandatory user education, and creating EU-level repositories for performance data with standardized metrics. Additionally, Cultural-E partners advocate for dynamic thermal comfort standards, ongoing occupant feedback, expanded financial incentives, and district-level sector coupling to maximize greenhouse gas reductions and foster sustainable energy solutions.

The Cultural-E project has paved a clear path towards achieving climate neutrality for the EU building stock by 2050. This ambitious goal is now within reach, thanks to the integration of Plus Energy Buildings, which not only meet but exceed energy efficiency standards.

For the first time, the European Commission has introduced a commissioner responsible for both energy issues and housing accessibility from an economic perspective. The Cultural-E Plus Energy Building concept is fully aligned with this direction, proposing people-centric, cost-effective solutions that prioritize sufficiency over efficiency as a mean to enable affordable housing.

In conclusion, the Cultural-E project has laid a robust foundation for the future of Plus Energy Buildings. By addressing both energy and economic aspects and through the intelligent use of data, the project exemplifies a holistic and forward-thinking strategy that can guide the EU towards its climate neutrality goals by 2050.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Plus energy buildings definition infographic

- <https://www.cultural-e.eu/peb-definition/>

Annex 2. Plus Energy Building KPI - Factsheets

cultural
Fact sheet OCE_LR_1

SOLUTION SET 1

- Mechanical ventilation through a decentralized ventilation system
- Space heating and cooling through a centralized heat pump with water storage
- Air movement through ceiling fan

LOW-RISE BUILDING

3 floors, 7 dwellings
of 80-110m² each

OCEANIC GEO-CLUSTER

ENERGY, LOAD MATCHING AND GRID INTERACTION

Self-generation
Self-consumption

Primary energy

Final energy

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Global Warming Potential (GWP)

Dynamic GWP

INDOOR COMFORT

Thermal comfort
Relative Humidity comfort

ECONOMIC IMPACT

Overall cost

Investment cost

THE RESIDENTS' VOICES

Conflicting practices

NEED
Ventilating and being in contact with the outdoor space

RESPONSE
Opening windows

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N. 870072.

Other factsheets examples available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/8273531>

Annex 3. PEB HUB

eurac research Home Plus Energy Building HUB Take the quiz EN

Plus Energy Buildings What is a Plus Energy Building Design Guidelines Join the community About

Plus Energy Building HUB
 Discover real cases of buildings that produce more energy than they consume.

SEARCH FILTERS MAP

March 06, 2025 Broekerwinning fase 2 Belgium

March 05, 2025 Residenza 1 Girasoli Italy

March 06, 2025 Ekkeveien 116, Berum, Norway Norway

March 14, 2025 MustB0 - Résidence Philippe le Hardi France

March 13, 2025 Ostfildern-Ruit Germany

March 14, 2025 Palacio de los Miranda Spain

March 05, 2025 P 18 - Urban Quarter on Prielnitzweg in Stuttgart, Germany

March 05, 2025 SOLARHAUS - 76 Dwellings in Burlada Spain

March 06, 2025 SOLARHAUS 142 Spain

March 14, 2025 San Pedro Spain

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WHAT'S NEXT?

What is a PEB
 Discover what is a Plus Energy Building (PEB) and how it produces more energy than it consumes.
[LEARN MORE](#)

How to design a Plus Energy Building
 Learn the key principles and expert tips to design and construct fast and efficiently a comfortable building with positive energy balance.
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Join the community
 Are you the architect or building owner of a Plus Energy Building? Send us your building information and we will feature it here!
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Contact
 Eurac Research
 Viale Druso, 1 / Drossauflue 1
 39100 Bolzano / Bozen - Italy
 T +39 0471 055 035
 F +39 0471 055 099
 @ energyefficientbuilding@eurac.edu

<https://energyefficientbuilding.eurac.edu/en/pebhub/>